

iADOR yields diverse shape-selective solid Lewis acid catalysts

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ABSTRACT

Lewis acid catalysts convert biomass compounds to green chemicals and fuels. Among these catalysts, stannosilicate zeolites display high thermal stability and reusability. However, only a few Sn-zeolites can be prepared using conventional synthesis methods, preventing us from developing shape-selective stannosilicate catalysts. Here, we propose a synthetic approach toward shape-selective Sn-zeolite catalysts, leveraging the Assembly, Disassembly, Organization, Reassembly (ADOR) strategy. By combining isomorphous Sn incorporation (i) into germanosilicate zeolites UOV, IWW, and IWR in the A step with structural modification in the DOR steps, we targeted new Sn-zeolite structures with either parallel or intersecting 12- and 8-ring pores predominantly containing Lewis acid centers with hydrolyzed Sn-O-Si bonds. The shape-selective performance of the designed Sn-zeolite catalysts was experimentally assessed and theoretically rationalized in transformations of citronellal into citronellol by Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley reduction and into isopulegol isomers via intramolecular cyclization. Therefore, iADOR paves the way toward new zeolite catalysts with engineered Sn active sites for green chemistry.

1. Introduction

In the petrochemical industry, zeolites are widely applied as shape-selective solid acid catalysts for their uniform microporosity, thermal stability, and a tuneable chemical composition [1]. The shape selectivity of these crystalline microporous elementosilicates derives from steric hindrance in their channels, channel intersections, and cages and is directly related to their pore size [1,2]. Case in point, medium-pore Al-MFI, large-pore Al-BEA, and Al-MOR are commonly used in large-scale petrochemical processes, such as isomerization, acylation, and Friedel-Crafts alkylation of aromatic compounds [3]. But the compositional diversity and the reaction scope of these zeolite catalysts are continuously expanding far beyond those of aluminosilicates [4,5]. In addition to Ti-zeolites for phenol oxidation to hydroquinone and cyclohexanone ammoxidation to cyclohexanone oxime [6–9], zeolite catalysis research and development has yielded Sn-zeolites for aldol condensation and chemoselective redox reactions via carbonyl activation [10–13].

On a large scale, carbonyl reductions are mainly performed using (i) a noncatalytic approach with reducing agents such as LiAlH_4 and NaBH_4 , (ii) hydrogenation with H_2 over metal catalysts, or (iii) organometallic catalysis [14]. The drawbacks of these approaches are (i) the low chemical selectivity of the used stoichiometric reagents, which

necessitates the reaction to be performed at cryogenic temperatures; (ii) the flammability of hydrogen and special equipment needed for hydrogenation; (iii) laborious separation of the organometallic catalyst from the products. Nevertheless, in the laboratory, Sn-zeolites catalyze aldehyde and ketone conversion into their respective alcohols via Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley (MPV) reduction using secondary alcohols as hydrogen donors [5]. These zeolite catalysts are easily separated and regenerated, albeit displaying lower activity and selectivity than organometallic catalysts [14–17]. However, the shape- and chemo-selectivity of Sn-zeolite catalysts can be maximized by optimizing not only their porous architecture but also the coordination environment and configuration of Sn active sites [18].

Despite the promising catalytic behavior of Sn-substituted zeolites and extensive research on the incorporation of Sn atoms into zeolite frameworks, the number of Sn-zeolites remains rather limited compared to the broad range of structures currently known [10]. Two main factors may account for such a narrow scope of Sn-zeolites. On the one hand, incorporating Sn atoms into zeolite frameworks during hydrothermal crystallization requires optimizing synthesis conditions both to prepare the targeted crystalline material and to avoid the formation of catalytically inactive bulk SnO_2 species [10,19]. Therefore, only two structures have been intensively studied, namely the large-pore zeolite BEA (with intersecting 12-ring channels of 0.66×0.67 and 0.56×0.56 nm) and the

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medium-pore zeolite MFI (with intersecting 10-ring channels of 0.51×0.55 and 0.53×0.56 nm), even though several frameworks have been produced by direct hydrothermal synthesis, almost invariably with a Si/Sn ratio > 100 [5,20]. On the other hand, post-synthesis of Sn-zeolites with variable Si/Sn ratios is limited to zeolites with ≥ 12 -ring pores [10,19].

Notably, Sn-zeolites prepared by bottom-up or top-down synthesis may have several structurally and catalytically distinct Sn site configurations, such as ‘closed’ Sn(OSi)₄ and defective Sn(OH)_n(OSi)_{4-n} centers with hydrolyzed Si-O-Sn bonds [21]. Whether these defective Sn centers are formed by hydrolysis of ‘closed’ sites or in the presence of framework defects, such as stacking faults [21], their number positively correlates with the rates of Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of cyclic ketones, glucose-to-fructose isomerization [21–23] and MPV reduction of cyclic ketones [24]. Conversely, the number of ‘closed’ Sn sites correlates with the rate of aldol condensation of carbonyl compounds [23].

Given the limitations of the established synthesis methods for creating structurally diverse Sn-zeolites, this study aimed to develop a combined bottom-up/top-down synthesis approach towards new Sn-zeolites with potential applications in shape-selective catalysis using the ADOR chemistry toolbox [25,26] (Scheme 1). The ADOR method established over the last decade takes advantage of the hydrolytic instability of Ge-O bonds and of the clustering of Ge atoms within D4R units of zeolite frameworks, such as UTL [27–29], UOV [30,31], IWR [32], IWW [33,34], and others [35,36] to transform already synthesized (Assembled) zeolites into previously unattainable IPC zeolites (IPC = Institute of Physical Chemistry) by a sequence of steps: 1) selective hydrolysis of Ge-O bonds, (Disassembly); 2) reorganization of formed silica crystalline building-blocks (Organization); 3) condensation of crystalline building-blocks via calcination (Reassembly). Classical ADOR using hydrolysis of germanosilicate zeolites in acidic [28,37] or basic aqueous solution [35] was applicable to a few frameworks, while the vapor-phase-transport (VPT) technique was shown to be efficient for ADOR transformation of various germanosilicates [32,33]. In the VPT method, the Disassembly of the parent zeolite is initiated by selective hydrolysis of SiO-Ge bonds with acid vapor (12 M HCl water solution with $p_{H_2O} = 10$ mm Hg and $p_{HCl} = 23$ mm Hg at 303 K [38]) leading to the rearrangement of D4R units into shorter interlayer connections and formation of new zeolites with smaller micropore sizes [33]. For example, VPT treatment of UTL zeolite with nonporous layers yielded IPC-7 material with alternating D4R/S4R units [33]. In contrast, germanosilicates featuring porous silica layers undergo transformation into zeolites with interlayer S4R units (i.e., IWW-to-IPC-17 [33] and IWR-to-IPC-17 [32] conversion) or O-bridges (i.e., UOV-to-IPC-12 conversion [33]). Notably, the UOV-, IWR- and IWW-derived IPC-n zeolites contain parallel or intersecting 12- and 8-ring pore, which are promising

for application in shape-selective catalysis after incorporation of appropriate active centers, e.g. Sn.

For that reason, this study focused on the extending the ADOR approach for the preparation of Lewis acid Sn-zeolites based on UOV, IWR, and IWW frameworks. For that, the isomorphous incorporation of Sn (i) into UOV, IWR, and IWW germanosilicate zeolites, *Assembly*, was followed by a structural transformation into new Sn-zeolites through the *Disassembly-Organization-Reassembly* steps (*iADOR* strategy) using the VPT method (Scheme 1) [33]. The incorporation of Sn atoms into the frameworks of UOV, IWW, and IWR germanosilicate zeolite in the *Assembly* step was shown to be crucial for designing new zeolite catalysts with engineered active centers because it enables full utilization of the ADOR chemistry not only for controllable structural modification of the parent framework, but also for achieving specific configurations of Sn acid sites (*vide infra*). Thus prepared *iADOR* Sn-zeolites (Fig. 1) were characterized by X-ray diffraction, nitrogen physisorption, scanning (SEM), and transmission (TEM) electron microscopy, IR spectroscopy of adsorbed probe molecules and UV-vis spectroscopy, while their shape-selective catalytic performance was experimentally assessed and theoretically rationalized in the transformations of citronellal into citronellol by MPV reduction and into isopulegol isomers *via* intramolecular cyclization, two routes affected by the zeolite pore size [39].

2. Experimental section

2.1. Preparation of organic structure-directing agents

Decamethonium dihydroxide (DMDH) and hexamethonium dihydroxide (HMDH) were used as SDAs to synthesize UOV [40] and IWW [41] zeolites, respectively. For that, commercially available decamethonium bromide (>98%, TCI Chemical) and hexamethonium bromide (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) were transformed to hydroxide forms by ion exchange with Ambersep® 900(OH) anion-exchange resin (Alfa Aesar). As-purchased 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU, 98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was used as structure-directing agents for the synthesis of IWR zeolite [42].

2.2. Synthesis of Sn-zeolites for *iADOR*

Sn-UOV. To determine the optimal conditions for crystallization of Sn-UOV zeolite, the molar composition of the reaction mixture was varied as follows: $(0.6 - x) \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.6 \text{ GeO}_2 : x \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.25 \text{ DMDH} : 10 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, $x = 0 - 0.012$. Either tin (IV) chloride pentahydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) or tin (II) chloride dihydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was used as the source of Sn. The resulting gel crystallized at 175 °C under tumbling (60 rpm) for 7 – 14 days.

Scheme 1. The proposed *iADOR* synthesis method for the preparation of Sn-zeolite catalysts (left) and schematic representation of the Vapour Phase Transport (VPT) treatment used at the Disassembly and Organization steps (right).

Zeolite		Interlayer connections	Channel dimension	
Sn-UOV		D4R	(12+8) X 10-ring	
Sn-IPC-12		Oxygen bridge		(12+8)- ring
Sn-IWR		D4R	12 X 10 X 10-ring	
Sn-IPC-17		S4R		12 X 8 X 8-ring
Sn-IWW		D4R	(12+8)X 10-ring	
Sn-IPC-18		S4R		(12+8) X 8-ring

Fig. 1. Sn-zeolites prepared in this study; daughter iADOR Sn-IPC-n zeolites retain the channel dimensions of their parent zeolites in the crystallographic direction perpendicular to the crystalline layers (shown in black), but show smaller “interlayer” channels (shown in brown).

Phase-pure Sn-UOV zeolite was synthesized by mixing an aqueous 1 M SDA solution (14.63 g) with 3.22 g of germanium (IV) oxide (99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich) at 400 rpm in a polypropylene beaker equipped with a mechanical stirrer at room temperature for 10 min and then adding an aqueous solution of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.12 g, 1:3 w/v) dropwise. Subsequently, 2.76 g of CAB-O-SIL® M-5 fumed silica (Thermo Scientific) was gradually added to the mixture and stirred for 8–14 h until the reaction mixture reached the required chemical composition by evaporating excess water. The resulting gel with a molar composition of $0.6 \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.6 \text{ GeO}_2 : 0.006 \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.25 \text{ DMDH} : 10 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ was charged in a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized at 175 °C under tumbling at 60 rpm for 14 days. The final product was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried at 60 °C, and calcined in the oven at 550 °C in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

Sn-IWW. To determine the optimal conditions for crystallizing Sn-IWW zeolite, the molar composition of the reaction mixture was varied as follows: $(0.8 - x) \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.4 \text{ GeO}_2 : x \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.225 \text{ HMDH} : 5 \text{ H}_2\text{O} : y \text{ HF}$ ($x = 0 - 0.012$; $y = 0$ or 0.5). Either tin (IV) chloride pentahydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) or tin (II) chloride dihydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was used as the source of Sn. The resulting gel was crystallized at 175 °C under tumbling (60 rpm) for 7–14 days.

Phase-pure Sn-IWW zeolite was synthesized by mixing a 1 M aqueous solution of HMDH (34.67 g) with 3.34 g of germanium (IV) oxide (99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich) at 400 rpm in a polypropylene beaker equipped with a mechanical stirrer at room temperature for 10 min and adding an aqueous solution of 0.13 g of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:3 w/v) dropwise. Subsequently, 12.01 g of colloidal silica Ludox® AS-40 (40 wt.% suspensions in H_2O , Sigma Aldrich) was added, and the mixture was kept stirred for 8–14 h until evaporating the excess of water; then, 0.3 g of HF (48 wt.% in water, $\geq 99.99\%$, Sigma Aldrich) was added. With a molar composition of $0.8 \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.4 \text{ GeO}_2 : 0.008 \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.225 \text{ DMDH} : 5 \text{ H}_2\text{O} : 0.5 \text{ HF}$, the suspension was charged in a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized at 175 °C for 14 days under tumbling at 60 rpm. The final product was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried at 60 °C, and calcined in the oven at 550 °C in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

Sn-IWR. 3.34 g of germanium (IV) oxide (99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich) was stirred in 4.87 g of a 1,8-Diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) aqueous solution (1:3 w/v) at 400 rpm in a polypropylene beaker equipped with a mechanical stirrer at room temperature for 10 min. Then, an aqueous solution of 0.14 g of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:3 w/v) was added dropwise, followed by adding 13.33 g of tetraethyl orthosilicate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) to the mixture. The reaction mixture was kept stirring for an additional 2–3 h until the ethanol evaporated. The resulting gel with

a molar composition of $0.8 \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.4 \text{ GeO}_2 : 0.008 \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.4 \text{ DBU} : 10 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ was charged in a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized at 175 °C under tumbling at 60 rpm for 14 days. The final product was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried at 60 °C, and calcined in the oven at 550 °C in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

2.3. Synthesis of reference Sn-zeolite catalysts

Sn-MFI. Sn-MFI zeolite was prepared as previously described [43], using a reaction mixture with a molar composition of $1.0 \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.01 \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.45 \text{ TPAOH} : 35 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$. For this purpose, 0.24 g of tin (IV) chloride pentahydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 9 ml of water and mixed with 15.12 g of tetraethyl orthosilicate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) at 400 rpm in a polypropylene beaker equipped with a magnetic stirrer at room temperature for 30 min. Subsequently, 16.27 g of tetrapropylammonium hydroxide solution (40 wt.% in water, Sigma Aldrich) was added and stirred for 1 h before adding 26 ml of distilled H_2O . The reaction mixture was kept under stirring for another 30 min, then charged in a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized for 10 days at 160 °C under static conditions. The final product was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried at 60 °C, and calcined in the oven at 550 °C in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

2.4. Sn-BEA

Sn-BEA zeolite was prepared as previously described [11]. Briefly, 10.76 g of tetraethyl orthosilicate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was added to 11.5 g of tetrapropylammonium hydroxide solution (35 wt.% in water, Sigma Aldrich), and the mixture was continuously stirred at 400 rpm in a polypropylene beaker equipped with a mechanic stirrer at room temperature for 2 h. 0.038 g of tin (II) chloride dihydrate (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 2 ml of ethanol and added dropwise to the mixture. Then, the excess ethanol and water were evaporated while the reaction mixture was exposed and stirred at room temperature for 8–14 h. Subsequently, 1.09 g of HF (48 wt.% in water, $\geq 99.99\%$, Sigma Aldrich) was gradually added, and the mixture with a molar composition of $1 \text{ SiO}_2 : 0.0033 \text{ SnO}_2 : 0.54 \text{ TEOAH} : 0.54 \text{ HF} : 7.52 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ was stirred for 5 min with a spatula. Lastly, zeolite seeds were added to the mixture, stirred with a spatula for five minutes. Commercial BEA (ZEOLYST, Si/Al = 68) was dealuminated in 65 wt.% nitric acid ($> 98\%$, Lachner) at 80 °C for 16 h and used as seeds. The mixture was loaded in a Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and crystallized at 140 °C for 9 days under tumbling at 60 rpm. The final product was filtered, washed

with distilled water, dried at 60 °C, and calcined in the oven at 550 °C in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of 2 °C•min⁻¹.

2.5. VPT treatment of Sn-zeolites

The VPT method [33] was used in the iADOR transformation of Sn-UOV into Sn-IPC-12, Sn-IWW into Sn-IPC-18, and Sn-IWR into Sn-IPC-17 (Scheme 1). For this purpose, 100 mg of the calcined zeolite were placed on a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) membrane filter (0.2 μ, STERLITECH) in a reactor over 10 ml of 12 M HCl solution (35 wt.%, Lechner). The VPT treatment of Sn-UOV, Sn-IWR, and Sn-IWW proceeded at room temperature for 16 h leading to the precursors of iADOR zeolites designated as Sn-IPC-12P [30], Sn-IPC-17P [32], and Sn-IPC-18P [33], respectively. The collected Sn-IPC-12P, Sn-IPC-17P, and Sn-IPC-18P samples were calcined for 2 h at 450 °C at a heating rate of 2 °C•min⁻¹ to form Sn-IPC-12, Sn-IPC-18 and Sn-IPC-17 zeolites, respectively.

To assess how the configuration of Sn acid sites and the pore sizes of the zeolite affect the outcome of citronellal transformation, Sn-BEA and Sn-MFI were subjected to the VPT treatment under the same conditions as stannogermosilicate zeolites, leading to different distributions of Sn centers between 'closed' and defective configurations. The respective samples were designated as Sn-MFI/VPT and Sn-BEA/VPT.

2.6. Characterization

The phase purity of all catalysts was determined by powder X-ray diffraction. X-ray patterns were collected using Cu Kα radiation (λ = 1.54056 Å) in Bragg-Brentano geometry on a Bruker AXS D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE-T detector. The experiments were conducted in continuous scanning mode in the range of 3 – 40° 2θ.

The N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms were collected at –196 °C on a 3Flex (Micromeritics) static volumetric instrument. All samples were degassed in a Micromeritics Smart Vac Prep instrument at T = 250 °C for 8 h before the sorption tests. Based on adsorption data, the micropore and mesopore volumes were determined using the t-plot method [44].

SEM images were acquired on a JEOL JSM-IT800 instrument using a secondary electron detector. The samples were placed on copper stubs with sticky carbon tape to increase the conductivity.

The chemical composition of the catalysts was determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS; Thermo-Scientific iCAP 7000) analysis. A closed vessel containing a mixture of 50 mg of zeolite, 1.8 ml of HF, 5.4 ml of HCl, and 1.8 ml of HNO₃ was placed in a microwave oven to dissolve the zeolite. To complex the HF surplus after cooling down, 16 ml of H₃BO₃ was added and reheated in the microwave oven.

STEM imaging was performed under a JEOL JEM NEOARM 200F microscope operated at 200 kV.

Diffuse reflectance ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) spectra were collected in the wavelength range of 200 – 600 nm on a Varian 4000 UV-vis spectrometer (Agilent) and converted into absorption spectra using the Kubelka-Munk function.

The configuration of Lewis acid sites in zeolite samples was determined by FTIR spectroscopy of adsorbed probe molecules. The samples were pressed into self-supporting wafers with a density of 10 mg•cm⁻² and activated *in situ* for 4 h at 450 °C, and 5•10⁻⁵ Torr. Pyridine (Py, ≥ 99.5 %, Penta) and d₃-acetonitrile (AN, ≥ 99.9 %, Sigma Aldrich) were used as probe molecules. AN adsorption was performed at room temperature for 20 min at a partial pressure of 5 Torr, followed by desorption for 20 min at the same temperature. Py adsorption was performed for 20 min at a partial pressure of 3.5 Torr at 150 °C, followed by desorption at the same temperature for 20 min. Spectra were acquired on a Nicolet iS50 spectrometer with a transmission MCT/B

detector, at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, collecting 128 scans per spectrum. The collected spectra were processed using Thermo Scientific Omnic 8.2 software. To estimate the fraction of Sn Lewis acid sites in different configurations, a Gaussian line shape was used for spectra deconvolution, thus calculating the area of the characteristic peaks (Table 1). The centers of the bands were fixed within 5 cm⁻¹, and the total widths at half maximum ranged from 5 to 20 cm⁻¹. The fraction of Sn Lewis acid sites in different configurations was estimated on the bases of the relative ratios of integral intensities of the characteristic bands in the FTIR spectra of adsorbed AN (Table 1).

H₂-TPR analysis was performed on an AMI-300 LITE catalyst characterization instrument by Altamira Instruments. A thermocouple-equipped quartz U-shaped measurement tube was filled with 100 mg of the sample and placed inside the oven. Before reduction, the samples were pretreated at 450 °C (10 °C•min⁻¹) in 5% O₂ (99.995%, Linde) and Ar (99.999%, Linde) for 1 h and then cooled down to room temperature under Ar flow. In each H₂-TPR run, the sample was heated from room temperature to 1000 °C at a temperature ramp of 10 °C•min⁻¹ under 5.02% H₂/Ar flow (15 ml•min⁻¹). H₂ (99.999%) was purchased from Linde.

2.7. Catalytic tests

The citronellal transformation was performed in a 25 ml round-bottom glass batch reactor using a Star-Fish multi-experiment workstation (Radleys Discovery Technologies). Consisting of 2.21 mmol of citronellal (96 %, Alfa Aesar), 6 ml of isopropyl alcohol (>99.9 %, VWR Chemicals) and 1.3 mmol of mesitylene (internal standard, 98%, Sigma Aldrich), the reaction mixture was heated to 70 °C under vigorous agitation with a magnetic stirrer, adding 50 mg of catalyst after reaching the reaction temperature. Before the test, all catalysts were activated at 450 °C for 6 h at a rate of 5 °C•min⁻¹. A gas chromatograph (Agilent 6890) with a nonpolar HP-5 column (30 m length, 0.320 mm diameter, and 0.25 μm film thickness) and a flame ionization detector were used to analyze reaction aliquots taken at regular intervals during the reaction. Reaction products were identified on a Thermo Scientific ISQ LTTRACE 1310 GC/MS.

The conversion (X), yield (Y), selectivity (S), and turn-over frequency (TOF) values were calculated according to the following equations:

$$X (\%) = [(n(\text{reactant})_0 - n(\text{reactant})_t) / n(\text{reactant})_0] * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$Y (\%) = [n(\text{product})_t / n(\text{reactant})_0] * 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S (\%) = [Y/X] * 100 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{TOF} (\text{h}^{-1}) = [n(\text{reactant})_0 - n(\text{reactant})_{1h}] / n (\text{Sn in 50 mg catalyst}) \quad (4)$$

(where: n (reactant)₀ and n (reactant)_t are the amounts of the reactant in the reaction mixture initially and after a specific time t; n(product)_t is the amount of the product formed after a specific time t; and n (Sn in 50 mg catalyst) is the amount of Sn in 50 mg of the catalyst determined by ICP-MS analysis. n(reactant) and n(product) values in Eq. 1, 2, 4, and 5 were determined based on the internal standard calibration method, using mesitylene (98 %, Sigma Aldrich) as an internal standard and commercially available citronellal (96 %, Alfa Aesar), citronellol (92%,

Table 1

Characteristic bands in the IR spectra of probe molecules adsorbed in Sn-BEA zeolite and their assignment to different configurations of Sn Lewis acid sites (LAS) [22,45].

Probe molecule	Type of sites as assigned in Sn-BEA zeolite	Peak center (cm ⁻¹)
AN	Sn(OH)(SiO) ₃	2316
	Sn(SiO) ₄	2306
	SnO _x or Sn(OH) ₂ (SiO) ₂	2285
Py	Sn LAS	1450, 1610

TCI), and isopulegol (97%, Alfa Aesar).

2.8. Computational analysis

Density functional local optimizations of isolated and zeolite-intercalated product molecules were performed using the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP 5.4) with projector-augmented wave (PAW) pseudopotentials [46–48]. The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (generalized gradient) exchange correlation functional [49], supplemented with Grimme's D3 dispersion correction (with BJ damping [50]), was applied to treat the electronic structure. The convergence criteria were 10^{-2} eV \AA^{-1} 10^{-5} eV for forces and energies, respectively. The Brillouin zone was sampled using the Gamma point only. Simulations of conformers were performed with the universal force field (UFF) within the mol-ellipse package and processed via in-house analysis software (described in the ESI).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Assembly of Sn-zeolites UOV, IWW, IWR

Synthesis conditions were optimized for isomorphous Sn incorporation into the frameworks of germanosilicate UOV, IWW, and IWR parent materials to prepare new Sn-containing zeolite catalysts *via* the *i*ADOR approach. For this purpose, we varied the source of Sn (e.g., $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), (Si+Ge)/Sn ratios, and the duration of hydrothermal crystallization while simultaneously maintaining the Si/Ge ratio at 1 for Sn-UOV [31] and 2 for Sn-IWW [51] and Sn-IWR [32] to ensure that a sufficient number of hydrolytically unstable linkages were available in the parent zeolites for their *i*ADOR transformation.

Sn incorporation slowed down UOV, IWW, and IWR crystallization, as previously reported for Sn-BEA zeolites [52]. Although highly crystalline materials were obtained in Sn-free germanosilicate systems within 7 days (PXRD in Fig. S1, a), the materials resulting from reaction mixtures with 1 mol.% Sn (using either Sn source, whether $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were amorphous (PXRD in Fig. S1, b). Prolonging crystallization up to 8–14 days yielded SnO_2 as an admixture of the targeted UOV zeolite phase (PXRD in Fig. S2, a) or as the only crystalline phase (PXRD in Fig. S2, b) when using $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a Sn source (0.5 mol.% Sn). The SnO_2 cassiterite phase was identified in the respective zeolitic materials by the characteristic diffraction peaks in their PXRD patterns (Fig. S2) and manifested as a broad absorption band at 280 nm in their UV-vis spectra [53].

Unlike $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ offered highly crystalline, phase-

pure zeolites at (Si+Ge)/Sn = 200 for Sn-UOV and at 150 for Sn-IWW and Sn-IWR (Fig. 2, a).

Further attempts to incorporate more Sn into UOV, IWW, and IWR frameworks using hydrothermal crystallization failed. More specifically, decreasing the (Si+Ge)/Sn ratio in the reaction mixture below 200 for Sn-UOV or 150 for Sn-IWW and Sn-IWR formed an admixed SnO_2 phase. In turn, diffuse-reflectance UV-vis spectra of Sn-zeolites prepared under optimized conditions showed the dominant absorption band centered at 210 nm (Fig. 2, b), which is assigned to tetrahedrally coordinated Sn atoms in zeolite framework positions [53,54].

Sn-UOV, Sn-IWW, and Sn-IWR showed micropore volumes similar to Sn-free zeolites (Table 2), but larger crystals (Fig. S3) formed due to the longer crystallization (14 vs. 7 days). Sn incorporation into Sn-UOV, Sn-IWW, and Sn-IWR frameworks yielded Sn Lewis acid sites, as shown by Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy of adsorbed pyridine (Fig. S4) and d_3 -acetonitrile (*vide infra*). The pyridine spectra of Sn-zeolites revealed pronounced absorption bands at 1610 and 1450 cm^{-1} attributed to the Sn Lewis acid sites [22]. In contrast, those bands were absent in the spectra of Sn-free zeolites measured under similar conditions (that is, pyridine ad-/desorption at 150 °C).

Table 2

Chemical composition and textural characteristics of Sn-free and Sn-containing UOV, IWR, IWW zeolites and their *i*ADOR daughters.

Zeolite	Chemical composition of the samples ^a		Textural properties ^b		
	Si/Ge, mol/mol	Si/Sn, mol/mol	V_{micro} , $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	V_{meso} , $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	S_{ext} , $\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$
UOV	3.5	–	0.16	0.21	151
Sn-UOV	2.4	88	0.15	0.14	101
Sn-IPC-12	70.0	89	0.08	0.12	144
IWW	2.3	–	0.15	0.11	95
Sn-IWW	2.1	81	0.14	0.11	84
Sn-IPC-18	77.0	83	0.10	0.12	102
IWR	1.8	–	0.18	0.07	57
Sn-IWR	1.5	67	0.18	0.06	40
Sn-IPC-17	80.0	70	0.09	0.15	86
Sn-MFI ^c	–	50	0.15	0.09	48
Sn-MFI/VPT	–	53	0.13	0.10	126
Sn-BEA ^c	–	62	0.17	0.09	41
Sn-BEA/VPT	–	64	0.20	0.07	58

^a based on ICP-MS analysis.

^b based on nitrogen physisorption.

^c Reference materials.

Fig. 2. PXRD patterns (a) and UV-vis spectra (b) of samples prepared in Sn-containing reaction mixtures using $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the source of Sn at (Si+Ge)/Sn molar ratios of 200 for Sn-UOV, 150 for Sn-IWR and Sn-IWW. The PXRD patterns of reference zeolites without and with Sn at similar Si/Ge ratios are shown for comparison.

3.2. *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites: structural features and acidic properties

The structural transformation of Sn-UOV, Sn-IWR, and Sn-IWW into respective *i*ADOR zeolite precursors after the VPT treatment and then into *i*ADOR zeolites after calcination was revealed by the results of the X-ray diffraction analysis (Fig. 3, a). The PXRD patterns of the *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites matched those previously reported for Sn-free IPC-12 (UOV daughter with interlayer -O- bridges) [30], IPC-17 (IWR daughter with interlayer -S4R- units) [32], and IPC-18 (IWW daughter with interlayer -S4R- units) [33], respectively. After the structureless Le Bail fitting (performed using Jana2020 [55]) the PXRD patterns of *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-12, Sn-IPC-17, and Sn-IPC-18 zeolites (Fig. S5), we confirmed the changes in unit cell parameters, primarily in the dimension reflecting reduced interlayer spacing due to D4R conversion into S4R or -O-bridges (marked in red in Table S1). Sn incorporation into the structure may also have a small effect, but such a contribution should be relatively insignificant given the low Sn concentrations, with less than one Sn per unit cell across all *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites.

STEM images provided further evidence of the *i*ADOR transformation of the parent stannogermanosilicates into the respective daughter zeolites. For example, views perpendicular to the unaltered layers highlighted intact pores, further supporting the premise of retained intralayer crystallinity (Fig. 4, top panel).

Additionally, the interlayer spacing (Fig. 4, bottom panel) of all materials derived from STEM images agreed with our PXRD results and corroborated values previously reported in other studies [30,32,33].

As in previous reports on germanosilicate ADOR [30,32,33], the channel system changed during the *i*ADOR structural transformation of the parent stannogermanosilicates into daughter zeolites (Fig. 1), but not the morphology or crystal size (Fig. 5).

The parent Sn-UOV and Sn-IWW zeolites showed 3D pore systems with 8- and 12-ring channels across the layers and the “interlayer” 10-ring channels (Fig. 1). In the daughter *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites, the 8- and 12-ring pores were not affected by the *i*ADOR rearrangement, whereas the 10-ring channels changed into 6- (not classified as pores because they are too small in Sn-IPC-12) or 8-ring (in Sn-IPC-18) channels. This change results from the substitution of the interlayer D4R units with i) oxygen bridges after transforming Sn-UOV into *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-12 or ii) S4Rs after Sn-IWW conversion into *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-18. In the parent Sn-IWR zeolite, the 3D pore system is formed by 12-ring pores going through the layers and a pair of ‘interlayer’ 10-ring channels. After the rearrangement of Sn-IWR (with D4R interlayer units) into Sn-IPC-17 (with S4R interlayer units), the 12-ring channels were preserved, but the ‘interlayer’ 10-ring pores were transformed into a pair of

intersecting 8-ring channels.

Importantly, both the parent and daughter *i*ADOR UOV- and IWW-derived Sn-zeolites exhibited similar mesopore volumes (Table 2) and characteristic type I nitrogen adsorption isotherms, indicative of microporous materials (Fig. S6). In line with change in zeolite topology, *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-12 and Sn-IPC-18 showed lower micropore volumes than their parent Sn-UOV and Sn-IWW zeolites, respectively. Notably, Sn-IPC-17 showed a marked increase in mesopore volume compared to the parent Sn-IWR zeolite (0.15 vs. 0.06 cm³•g⁻¹) suggesting partial degradation of the zeolite framework under the VPT conditions. This result is likely caused by the limited hydrolytic resistance of the thin crystals shown by Sn-IWR (Fig. 5) as previously reported in [32]. Therefore, the pronounced decrease in the micropore volume of Sn-IPC-17 vs. Sn-IWR can be related to both the decrease in micropore sizes and partial amorphization of the zeolite upon the Sn-IWR-to-Sn-IPC-17 transformation.

Chemical analysis revealed a strong increase in the Si/Ge ratio (from 1.5 – 2.4 to 70 – 80) and a marginal increase in the Si/Sn ratio (Table 2) after *i*ADOR transformation under VPT conditions (Scheme 1). The result can be explained by hydrolysis of SiO-Ge bonds under the action of acid vapor and by the removal of Ge from the zeolite framework in the form of volatile germanium chloride (bp_{GeCl₄} = 359 K, for pure GeCl₄ p_{GeCl₄} = 94 mm Hg at 303 K [56]). Similarly to Ge-O(Si) bonds, Sn-O(Si) bonds are known to be hydrolytically unstable, but undergo only partial (that is, breaking of only one of four siloxane bonds around the Sn center) rather than complete hydrolysis (that is, breaking of all four siloxane bonds around the Ge center) [57]. Furthermore, the low volatility of SnCl₄ (bp_{SnCl₄} = 387 K, for pure SnCl₄ p_{SnCl₄} = 26 mm Hg at 303 K [56]) may be another factor that prevents the removal of Sn from a zeolite under the used VPT conditions (Table 2).

The following results confirmed the absence of extra-framework SnO₂ species in the parent and *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites: i) UV-vis spectroscopy (Fig. 6, a) demonstrating the narrow absorption band at 210 nm characteristic of the tetrahedrally coordinated framework Sn atoms; ii) H₂ temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-TPR; Fig. 6, b) showing two broad high-temperature peaks at 500 – 600 and 650 – 1000 °C, which were assigned to the reduction of framework Ge(IV) and Sn(IV) species, according to previous reports [54,58,59]. The interaction of H₂ with small dispersed SnO_x particles, which usually manifests as a low-temperature peak at <500 °C, was not observed in the H₂-TPR profiles of the parent stannogermanosilicates or the daughter Sn-IPC-n zeolites [60].

We gained further insight into the configuration of Sn Lewis acid sites in the parent and daughter *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-n zeolites by FTIR

Fig. 3. PXRD patterns (a) and nitrogen ad-/desorption isotherms (b) of *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-12, Sn-IPC-17, and Sn-IPC-18 zeolites. The PXRD patterns of the respective parent Sn-zeolites and *i*ADOR zeolite precursors Sn-IPC-nP are provided for comparison.

Fig. 4. STEM images of *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites showing an intact pore system (top panel) and interlayer spacings (bottom panel).

Fig. 5. SEM images of the parent and respective daughter *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites.

spectroscopy of adsorbed d_3 -acetonitrile (Fig. 7, a). Following the approach proposed by Bates et al. [21], the acquired FTIR spectra of adsorbed d_3 -acetonitrile were deconvoluted into several components (Fig. S7) to estimate the distribution of Sn sites among different configurations. In particular, the adsorption of d_3 -acetonitrile in these Sn-zeolites generated several bands attributed to $C \equiv N$ groups coordinated with Sn Lewis acid sites (2310 and 2285 cm^{-1}) [22,45,61], silanol groups (2277 cm^{-1}) and physisorbed d_3 -acetonitrile (2266 cm^{-1}).

In most Sn-BEA zeolites studied to date, the broad asymmetric band at 2310 cm^{-1} has been unambiguously shown to consist of 2 overlapping bands, one at 2316 cm^{-1} , assigned to the $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})(\text{SiO})_3$ sites, and another at 2306 cm^{-1} , assigned to the ‘closed’ $\text{Sn}(\text{SiO})_4$ sites [21,22]. But there is still no consensus on the assignment of the band at ~ 2285 cm^{-1} . This band has been attributed to weak Lewis acid sites in extra-framework SnO_2 species [45]. However, in this study, such species

were not detected in either parent or daughter *i*ADOR zeolites by UV–vis spectroscopy (Figs. 2, b and 6, a), XRD (Figs. 2, a and 3, a) or H_2 -TPR analysis (Fig. 6, b).

After ruling out the assignment to extra-framework SnO_2 species, we considered two other possibilities. Some authors have attributed this band to SiOH groups near the $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})(\text{SiO})_3$ sites because the acidity of these silanol groups is significantly higher than that of silanol moieties at the external surface or within the lattice defects [62]. Others, conversely, have assigned this band to double-hydrolyzed framework $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{SiO})_2$ sites [22]. Based on our data, we cannot conclude as to whether one or the other assignment is correct, but regardless of the exact configuration of the Sn sites, these sites contain hydrolyzed Sn–O–Si bonds and are therefore defective.

A key feature observed in the *i*ADOR transformation of stannogermanosilicate zeolites was an increase in the fraction of defective Sn

Fig. 6. UV-vis spectra of *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites with different pore systems (a) and H₂-TPR profiles of Sn-IWW and *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-18 zeolites (b).

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of Sn-zeolites in the $C \equiv N$ vibration region after AN adsorption (a), and distribution of Sn acid sites among different configurations based on FTIR-AN data (b).

acid centers with hydrolyzed Sn-O-Si bonds (absorption band at 2316 cm^{-1} for Sn-IPC-18 and absorption band at 2285 cm^{-1} for Sn-IPC-12 and Sn-IPC-17 in the FTIR spectra of d_3 -acetonitrile, Fig. 7b) with respect to the number of ‘closed’ Sn(OSi)₄ sites (absorption band at 2306 cm^{-1}). The formation of single-hydrolyzed Sn(OH)(SiO)₃ sites and their subsequent transformation into Sn(OH)₂(SiO)₂ species during the *i*ADOR transformation of stannogermanosilicates may be favorable because the Ge-O-Sn(Si) bonds abundantly found in the frameworks of parent zeolites are readily hydrolyzed (Si/Ge = 1.5 – 2.4, Table 2). And, as in the incomplete condensation of Q3 and Q2 silanol defects that occurs during the Reassembly step of different Sn-free germanosilicate zeolites subjected to ADOR [30,33,63], the proximal Si-OH groups may not allow condensation with the Sn(OH)(SiO)₃ and/or Sn(OH)₂(SiO)₂ sites, thus preventing the formation of tetrahedral ‘closed’ configurations. Consistently with the plausible mechanism of defective Sn acid site formation upon *i*ADOR transformation, all the designed Sn-IPC-*n* zeolites featured enhanced concentration of silanol groups compared to the parent Sn-UOV, Sn-IWW, Sn-IWR zeolites (Fig. S8).

Overall, our integrated synthetic approach enabled the design and synthesis of new Sn-zeolites with parallel (Sn-IPC-12) or intersecting 12- and 8-ring (Sn-IPC-17 and Sn-IPC-18) pores. These *i*ADOR materials primarily contain defective Sn sites with hydrolyzed Sn-O-Si bridges, which have been shown to outperform framework Sn(OSi)₄ sites in several reactions, including MPV reduction of carbonyl compounds [64, 65]. To date, defective Sn sites have only been selectively placed by post-synthesis of 12-ring BEC zeolite [66]. Moreover, such Lewis acid

sites have never been engineered in any known Sn-zeolite containing <12-ring pores.

Catalytic performance of designed Sn-zeolites. The catalytic performance of the *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites was assessed in the transformation of citronellal and compared to that of the reference Sn-BEA and Sn-MFI zeolite catalysts (Table 2). In principle, this model reaction can follow three competitive routes, namely [11,13,67] 1) MPV reduction to citronellol, which is used as a component of perfumes and fragrances; 2) intramolecular cyclization into isopulegol isomers; and 3) acetalization into citronellal diisopropylacetal (Fig. 8).

As shown in previous studies, the outcome of citronellal transformation depends on catalyst parameters, including the pore size and type of acid sites. The effect of pore size on this reaction pathway can be exemplified by zeolites with variable metal cations at ion-exchange positions, as Cs-exchanged aluminosilicate X zeolite yields citronellol (71% yield) *via* MPV reduction (route 1), whereas Na-exchanged zeolite X promotes the selective formation of isopulegol (75% yield) through intramolecular ring closure (route 2) [39]. In turn, the acetalization reaction (route 3) is catalyzed by both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites of different strengths [68,69], including weakly acidic silanol groups [70]. The connectivity of Sn Lewis acid sites to the framework is also crucial because the activity of these sites in MPV reduction increases in the following order: Sn(SiO)₄ < Sn(OH)(SiO)₃ < Sn(OH)₂(SiO)₂ [24,65].

Over Sn-free germanosilicate zeolites, no citronellal conversion was detected in this study, indicating inactive Ge sites in these transformations and under the specific conditions of the catalytic experiment.

Fig. 8. Possible routes of citronellal conversion over Sn-zeolites (top), namely Meerwein–Ponndorf–Verley reduction (orange), intramolecular cyclization (green) and acetalization (blue), and product selectivity at 15% conversion over the *i*ADOR (bottom, left) and reference (bottom, right) Sn-zeolite catalysts.

Inversely, citronellal underwent a selective transformation into isopulegols (99% selectivity at 15% conversion, Fig. 8) over Sn-UOV and Sn-IWW catalysts, whereas Sn-IWR catalyzed the formation of isopulegol (70% selectivity at 15% conversion) and to a lesser extent of acetal (15%) and citronellol (13%). The yield of the acetalization reaction over Sn-IWR was higher than over Sn-UOV and Sn-IWW possibly due to the higher fraction of weakly acidic silanol groups in Sn-IWR (Fig. S8). Similarly, all daughter *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites with an increased concentration of silanol groups provided a higher yield of acetal than the parent zeolites (20–40% vs. 1–15% over daughter vs. parent zeolites, respectively, Fig. 8). Furthermore, the *i*ADOR transformation markedly increased the fraction of citronellol produced over Sn-IPC-*n* catalysts (50–60%) when compared to the parent stannogermanosilicates (1–10%) while decreasing the selectivity for the intramolecular cyclization product (1–30% vs. 70–99% over daughter vs. parent zeolites, respectively).

In line with previous reports [24,39,66], we may explain why the selectivity of MPV reduction over *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-*n* zeolites is higher than over the parent materials based on their modified pore system, which provides shape selectivity, and/or on their increased concentration of more active defective Sn sites with hydrolyzed Sn–O–Si bridges. To test both hypotheses, we prepared two sets of reference catalysts with either

different micropore sizes (12-ring Sn-BEA and 10-ring Sn-MFI) or different types of Sn acid sites (Sn-BEA and Sn-BEA/VPT; Sn-MFI and Sn-MFI/VPT) and studied them in citronellal transformation.

Sn-BEA/VPT and Sn-MFI/VPT showed no change in their structure (Fig. S9), textural characteristics (Fig. S10), or crystal morphology (Fig. S11) compared to their parent Sn-BEA or Sn-MFI zeolites. However, FTIR spectra of adsorbed d_3 -acetonitrile showed differences in the distribution of the Sn sites between different configurations in Sn-BEA/VPT vs. Sn-BEA and in Sn-MFI/VPT vs. Sn-MFI (Fig. S12). In addition, the results of the catalytic tests (Fig. 8) demonstrated that the pore size of the zeolite, not the speciation of the Sn sites, strongly affects the selectivity of the citronellal transformation. More specifically, large-pore Sn-BEA and Sn-BEA/VPT zeolites with intersecting 12-ring pores were selective for the intramolecular cyclization route (90–95% selectivity at 15% conversion) regardless of the distribution of Sn sites.

In contrast to their large-pore counterparts, medium-pore Sn-MFI zeolites with intersecting 10-ring channels predominantly led to the formation of acetal (55–60%) and the MPV reduction product (35–38%). In fact, the *i*ADOR Sn-IPC-*n* materials not only showed a higher selectivity to citronellol than the reference Sn-BEA and parent stannogermanosilicate catalysts (Fig. 8) but also higher TOF values than Sn-MFI zeolite (Fig. S13). The higher TOFs of these Sn-IPC-*n* zeolites vs.

Sn-MFI may originate from the rapid transport of the reacting molecules through 12-ring pores.

To rationalize this pore size-dependent product selectivity, the molecular geometries of citronellol, isopulegol, and citronellal diisopropylacetal were simulated. The PBE-D3 local optimization of low energy single molecule configurations were done *in vacuo* (Figs. S14 and S15). The length of the second axis of the cylinder, which contains the molecular structure (Fig. S16), was defined as the critical diameter. After sampling 7500 conformers for each of the three molecules, we evaluated the critical diameter distribution (Fig. 9) and determined the mean (d_c^{mean} shown as vertical lines in Fig. 9) and minimum (d_c^{min} , Table S2) critical diameters.

The d_c^{mean} and d_c^{min} values showed different trends. d_c^{mean} increased from isopulegol (6.19 Å) to citronellol (7.40 Å), peaking with diisopropylacetal (10.36 Å), whereas d_c^{min} increased from citronellol (4.51 Å) to isopulegol (5.30 Å), peaking with diisopropylacetal (7.31 Å). Both d_c^{mean} and d_c^{min} values of diisopropylacetal exceeded the maximum sphere diameter for diffusion in all zeolites under study. Therefore, diisopropylacetal may be formed at the external surface of zeolites or at the pore mouths without being limited by the pore size constraints that affect selectivity to citronellol/ isopulegol.

The distribution of critical diameters was wider for citronellal than for isopulegol because linear molecules are geometrically more flexible than cyclic molecules. Citronellol has a higher mean diameter than the more rigid isopulegol but may nevertheless adopt configurations that allow citronellol to permeate through the small pores of Sn-IPC-n catalysts. This confinement-induced reconfiguration is reflected in the intercalation energies (E_{int}) of the molecules into the pores (Eq. (5)).

$$E_{int} = E_{mol@zeo} - E_{mol} - E_{zeo} \quad (5)$$

For configurations with the minimum critical diameter (Fig. S17), intercalation into IWR reached -84 kJ mol^{-1} for isopulegol, but only -48 kJ mol^{-1} for citronellol. However, in the daughter zeolite IPC-17, citronellol was bound considerably more strongly (-139 kJ mol^{-1}) than isopulegol (-25 kJ mol^{-1}). This difference implies that citronellol, thanks to its linear form, fits better into the narrower space of the daughter *i*ADOR zeolite than the parent and thus benefits from interactions with nearby framework atoms and that isopulegol is destabilized, both absolutely and relatively to citronellol, in the confined environment of the daughter zeolite. These assumptions are in line with the change in selectivity between these two products.

4. Conclusion

We can create catalytically active and shape-selective *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites by combining isomorphous Sn incorporation into germanosilicate zeolites featuring hydrolytically unstable Ge-O bonds preferentially located in D4R units in the A step with their structural transformation *via* DOR steps. These shape-selective catalysts are unattainable by conventional bottom-up hydrothermal crystallization or any method other than *i*ADOR. But in addition to introducing structural modifications to parent frameworks by reconstructing Ge-enriched D4R building units, *i*ADOR also enables us to tailor Sn acid centers with hydrolyzed Sn-O-Si bridges. These *i*ADOR Sn-zeolites contain either parallel (Sn-IPC-12) or intersecting 12- and 8-ring pores (Sn-IPC-17 and Sn-IPC-18) and show shape-selectivity in citronellal transformation, involving several competitive routes. Considering the structural diversity of germanosilicates that can be subjected to *i*ADOR and the possibility of engineering their specific active sites, this synthetic strategy will open up numerous opportunities to prepare new, shape-selective zeolite catalysts for green chemistry.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sarra Abdi: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding

Fig. 9. Histogram of the critical diameters of the three reaction products; the mean value is highlighted with a vertical line.

acquisition, Formal analysis. **Daniel N. Rainer:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martin Kubů:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Christopher J. Heard:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jiří Čejka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Mariya Shamzhy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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